

Analysis of Learning Interest Indonesian

Indar Listia Ningsih^{1*}, Eka Titi Andaryani

Universitas Negeri Semarang

Corresponding Author: Indar Listia Ningsih indar2818@students.unnes.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Indonesian,
Interest, Interest to learn

Received : 3, June

Revised : 18, July

Accepted: 18, August

©2023 Ningsih, Andaryani: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This study aims to find out information related to the learning interests of fifth grade students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 , Brebes Regency . This study uses a qualitative descriptive research method. Data collection techniques in this study, namely observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis techniques use the Miles and Huberman model. Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that (1) there is a link between interest and learning outcomes obtained by fifth grade students, namely already satisfactory as evidenced by the acquisition of scores above the KKM in the student master book. High learning outcomes are influenced by students' interest in learning Indonesian; (2) there are factors that cause interest in learning, namely internal factors from within students' self-intentions to learn Indonesian. While external factors from the outside are influenced by various teacher teaching methods, family environmental conditions that pay little attention to student learning styles, and the lack of completeness of infrastructure in schools; (3) the teacher's efforts to increase interest in learning Indonesian by holding literacy culture habituation before learning activities begin for fifteen minutes and the teacher directs students who have problems in reading comprehension to go to the library accompanied by the BP teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Education is important to support the progress of a nation . Through education, it is hoped that it can give birth to the next generation of nationals who are able to compete on the international stage. Especially in Indonesia, education is considered important to create a dignified (Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional, pasal 3)national civilization as stated in .

Various efforts to improve the quality of education in Indonesia have been carried out but cannot be separated of the inhibiting factors that emerged. For example , Indonesian is underestimated by students. Whereas, These subjects are important as a means of intercommunication individuals and society. In fact, according(Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional, pasal 37) obliges the primary and secondary education curricula to contain a language that refers to the subject, namely Indonesian .

Learning Indonesian is essentially part of the process of teaching language used in Indonesia. This knowledge studies something that refers to the achievement of Indonesian language goals . The main goal is to improve students' ability to communicate using Indonesian both orally and in English well (Susanto, 2019, hlm. 246)written .

Indonesian as one of the subjects taught at the elementary school level. Indonesian language lessons in elementary schools are essentially teaching children to be able to communicate using Indonesian. Indonesian language learning in elementary schools is directed at improving students' ability to communicate in Indonesian both orally and in writing. Orally means covering aspects of speaking and reading, while in writing , namely aspects of student writing. Elementary schools have the goal of creating or preparing students to have the ability to continue to a higher level of education. One of the efforts made to realize these goals is to increase students' interest in learning .

The teacher's various teaching methods are able to increase students' interest in learning Indonesian . Teachers who are used to teaching Indonesian using the lecture method alone can make students feel bored, passive, sleepy, and only take notes on (Slameto, 2020, hlm. 65)material . It is explained by (A.M, 2020, hlm. 14)that the components of interaction between teachers and students in teaching and learning activities must respond to and influence one another. Teacher teaching process in learning Indonesian requires the activeness of all students and teachers physically, mentally, emotionally, morally , and spiritually. Teachers as the main factor and students as learning objects are constrained by something that is considered to interfere with the teaching and learning process. One of them is the interest in learning Indonesian for each individual different, because not all students have the desire to learn at the same lesson.

The fact that happened to the fifth grade students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency was that not all students were interested in learning Indonesian , because some of these students were constrained by aspects of reading that were not fluent. Some students who are interested can

read fluently, while students who are less interested still read haltingly. Interest in learning related to aspects of students' reading causes students' reading comprehension skills to be low. Some students are reading haltingly, there were even fifth grade students who could not read could become obstacles or problems for students in participating in the learning process .

Teachers need to associate Indonesian language material with activities students are interested in in order to obtain a continuous sense of pleasure and satisfaction . According to (Risnanosanti dkk., 2022, hlm. 14)the emergence of interest in students can direct someone to carry out certain activities related to something he is interested in. If the interest is already owned by students , then it can be potential for the person concerned to achieve success in that field , because interest is able to generate great energy to struggle to get something he is interested in. Students who are interested in learning Indonesian will work hard to get the desired results.

The success of learning Indonesian is related to the role of the teacher who does not only act as the only source of learning, but also facilitates students to be interested in learning . Murwani In (Susanto, 2019, hlm. 25)teaching and learning activities the teacher must provide opportunities for students to learn as widely as possible and facilitate them to actualize themselves through the role of the teacher as a facilitator. The teacher's efforts to improve the quality of education, especially in Indonesian language lessons, require a learning process that is commensurate with optimal learning outcomes in accordance with the wishes of students. Good awareness from students as subjects who are actively involved in the learning process and teachers are needed, because learning is essentially an activity carried out consciously by a person to produce changes in behavior in himself, both knowledge, new skills and positive attitudes and values. . The effectiveness of the teaching and learning process is formed when all students are more active in participating in the learning process (Susanto, 2019, hlm. 49). Through student participation it is easier to understand lessons based on their own experience so as to increase interest in learning Indonesian .

The teacher when teaching Indonesian language material to fifth grade students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Kapupaten considers that Indonesian language subjects Most of the students have been able to master but some students considered difficult to understand . Class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency regarding their interest in learning Indonesian already exists , but some students cannot read fluently.

Here are some studies related to interest in learning Indonesian language which strengthens the writer to investigate interest in learning in Indonesian language subjects , among others carried out by (Astina dkk., 2021), (Warsadi, 2019), (Sutina dkk., 2022), (Harjanto dkk., 2021), and (Agustin dkk., 2021). One of them is research conducted by (Astina dkk., 2021) entitled " Increasing Student Interest in Indonesian Language Subjects Through Newspaper Media in Class III at Public Elementary School 119/VIII Tirta Kencana Rimbo Bujang ". The results of his research indicate that the interest in learning Indonesian in class III students at the school can be increased by using newspapers as media.

Research by (Warsadi, 2019) who examined three state junior high schools in Bogor City, namely: SMPN 5, SMPN 8, and SMPN 12 Bogor with the research title " Indonesian Language Learning Achievement: The Influence of Learning Interest and Learning Motivation ". The results of his research used the requirements analysis test through SPSS, examining the interest in learning and motivation to learn Indonesian achieved by students by looking at several factors influencing student achievement, especially in the Indonesian language subject .

Descriptive qualitative research entitled " Analysis of Learners' Learning Interests in Class IV Indonesian Subject at SDN 1 Wanasaba Daya Academic Year 2022/2023 " by (Sutina dkk., 2022) regarding indicators of interest learn r students while paying attention explanation Teacher in class , environmental conditions and their infrastructure and other factors that hinder students' success in learning language material Indonesian . Teachers can provide support and motivation to participant students in order to achieve increased learning outcomes and achievements.

Quantitative descriptive research entitled " Motivation, Independence, Interest in Learning and Learning Methods to The Learning Achievements of Students of SMA Batik 2 Surakarta " by (Harjanto dkk., 2021) discussing increasing students' interest and motivation in learning affects learning outcomes by using appropriateness in the learning methods taught by the teacher accompanied by student independence when learning.

Quantitative descriptive research entitled " The Role of Animated Interactive Media on the Learning Interests of Grade IV Students at SDN 019 Tanjung Sawit, Tapung District, Kampar District, 2020/2021 Learning " by (Agustin dkk., 2021) regarding the role of interactive animated media on the learning interests of Grade IV students at SDN 019 Tanjung Sawit in Indonesian language subjects can attract students' interest in learning Indonesian. When students show pleasure, interest, involvement and participation in learning Indonesian language subjects, students have an interest in learning and the role of animated interactive media is declared effective.

Based on interviews with fifth grade teachers at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency, most of the students were interested in learning Indonesian , but some students were not interested. The reason for this is the unsupportive family environment because both parents left them to wander until they were entrusted to their grandmother, grandfather or sibling who lived at home, the high level of difficulty when viewing reading material that was too long also made students feel bored, even some There are students in class V who cannot read fluently . The author is interested in conducting this research in order to find out the problem entitled "Analysis of Interest in Learning Indonesian for Class V Students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency".

Formulation of the problem

From the background that has been described, the formulation of the problem is as follows:

- 1) How What is the relationship between learning interest and learning outcomes of Indonesian language students in class V at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency?
- 2) How factors causing an interest in learning Indonesian in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency?
- 3) What are the teacher's efforts to increase interest in learning Indonesian in class V at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes District, Brebes Regency?

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

The author uses a qualitative descriptive research design . Sources of data used primary data and secondary data , for data collection this study used the method of observation, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used by researchers uses the Miles and Hubberman model in the form of data reduction, data presentation, as well as drawing conclusions and data verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The object of this study were 36 students in class V at SDN 01 Banjaranyar for the academic year 2022/2023. This research is guided by data originating from research instruments in the form of observation, interviews, and documentation.

Research Result

The Relationship between Learning Interest and Indonesian Language Learning Outcomes for Class V Students at SDN Banjaranyar, Brebes Regency Data on the link between interest in learning and learning outcomes in Indonesian were obtained through observation, initial interviews with fifth grade teachers , follow-up interviews with fifth grade teachers, follow-up interviews with school principals, and documentation. The author obtained data based on observation, interviews and documentation in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency. The following describes the results of observations , interviews , and documentation regarding the link between interest in learning and learning outcomes in Indonesian.

Learning interest is important in learning activities. The results of the analysis stated that there was a link between learning interest and student learning outcomes in Indonesian language subjects in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, which was in line with the opinion of the class V teacher who stated that:

" Yes ma'am. If a student has a high learning enthusiasm, a high interest in learning, if he is serious, then his learning results will be better. On the other hand, if students' interest decreases, their learning results will not be optimal ." (W.GKD)

Students' interest in learning is very influential on the results of learning Indonesian because the higher students have an interest in learning , the better the learning outcomes they have obtained. If students' interest decreases, their

Indonesian language learning outcomes will also be less than optimal and their grades will also decrease. Interest in learning is very important for teachers to know the high and low levels of interest related to the results of learning Indonesian obtained by students.

The class V teacher stated that:

" Yes ma'am. His name is also interested, of course he will continue to study the material until he gets learning achievements. Students who are interested are enthusiastic and want to get good grades. What's more, if there's a prize, sis, there are lots of people interested, of course hahah. (W. GKD)

Students who have a high interest in learning produce better learning achievements and learning outcomes as evidenced by the learning scores in the student manual that are superior to students who are less interested in asking or answering teacher questions. If student interest decreases, then learning outcomes and learning achievements become less than optimal.

In accordance with the opinion of the class V teacher, stated that:

Yes . Students who have a high learning interest will definitely produce good learning achievement results from superior grades compared to students who are less interested in asking or answering questions. (W. GKD)

Interest in learning is very important and influences the desires of students related to the success of the learning process. Interested students will generate great energy within themselves to obtain something in the form of value shown in good academic achievement. This is in accordance with the principal's opinion that:

"Yes very important." (W.KS)

Students who are interested will pay attention to the teacher's explanation and understand the material well which in the end will be able to obtain satisfying Indonesian learning results. The condition of students' interest in learning in class was explained by the class V teacher, who stated that:

Yes . The children in class V are very enthusiastic about learning Indonesian. " (W.GKS). Learning outcomes in Indonesian language lessons are closely related to student learning interest in terms of competence in reading and comprehension, because the more fluent students read, the higher their interest. This is in line with the fifth grade teacher, that:

Yes . Students who read fluently also have an increased interest in reading. " (W. GKS). Students who can read fluently are certain to be able to understand the material well, so the teacher is not too worried if the student is faced with a question or a long reading. Indonesian is studied as a subject matter that has the characteristics of long reading and deep understanding. In accordance with the opinion of the class V teacher, that:

" That's why I sometimes suggest that if you read it, you can digest it, understand it, what does it mean. So, if you understand the text, you will know the correct answer. But sometimes they find it difficult to read a lot, even though there are a lot of stories on the exam, it's actually misleading. If you read it, children can read the term at a glance but don't understand it, right? That's why it's like that. Actually, sometimes I direct the Indonesian language carefully to understand what the contents of the reading are, right? What's the

story, to bae now you can tell the reading back to bae kowen watching soap operas kuwe there is a storyline right? Yes ma'am. You can still tell the drama or soap opera from the beginning to the end, can you follow it. If you follow closely, you can tell your friends. It's a funny story, yes. You can tell a story because you understand, but the problem is that children are lazy to read, from an Indonesian perspective." (W.GKD)

Based on documentation data, the results of learning Indonesian for class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency, most students get satisfactory grades because the scores they get are above the KKM. Students who get satisfactory learning outcomes have an interest in learning, because it is related to the students' skills in reading fluently. Students who are unable to read fluently or haltingly make student learning outcomes unsatisfactory which results in a lack of student interest in learning Indonesian.

The results of learning Indonesian for class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency tend to be less than optimal because some students cannot read fluently. Some students are able to read fluently and the rest can read but still stammer. Indonesian language lessons have the characteristic of long reading considered by some students who feel that they are already fluent in reading they are able to master it. Most of the students scored above the KKM and most of them got higher marks than in other subjects, because Indonesian is still a subject that some students like in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes Regency.

Factors Causing Interest in Learning Indonesian Class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes Regency Data on the link between interest in learning and learning outcomes in Indonesian were obtained through observation, initial interviews with fifth grade teachers , follow-up interviews with fifth grade teachers, follow-up interviews with school principals, and documentation. The author obtained data based on observation, interviews and documentation in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency. The following describes the results of observations , interviews , and documentation about the factors that cause interest in learning Indonesian.

Interest in learning is very necessary in the process of learning Indonesian because you can find out the learning conditions and factors that cause students' interest in learning Indonesian in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01. These factors come from within and outside yourself. Students' interest in learning is influenced by their own factors in the form of assumptions about Indonesian language subjects easy to learn , so they only rely on reading literacy skills that are already fluent. Some students also feel difficulty understanding Indonesian language subjects .

This is in accordance with the statement of the class teacher, that: "The factor is usually not all students can read. There are still class V who are not yet fluent in reading. That's the problem." (W.GKS)

Students who have not been able to read fluently are able to influence student learning interest. Moreover, the characteristics of the Indonesian language contain long reading material, so it is difficult for students to get

satisfactory learning results.

However, in the opinion of the fifth grade teacher said that:
"Yes but not all of them. The term result is that sometimes there are smart ones who are not. Smart children usually understand reading quickly and not really low, sometimes what happens? Smart children master it easily, right, but if there are those who can't read fluently, it's difficult to understand. If you say it's very low, then no, it means it's medium." (W.GKD)

Student learning outcomes can be said to be unsatisfactory but not low. This means that students in class V at SDN Banjaranyar 01 do not all have the same level of intelligence and acceptance of the material. Some students understand the teacher's explanation and the rest still need further explanation. Each student has differences regarding hobbies or interests in a particular subject. Students who are interested in learning Indonesian material are able to follow the learning process well and have a high sense of enthusiasm as evidenced by the activeness of students in asking and answering teacher questions. The class V teacher also said that:

"If children are given Indonesian language lessons, they really pay attention to Ms. But I don't know how to accept it, sometimes there are those who pay attention, there are also those who talk to themselves, like that." (W.GKS)

Some students who are less interested in learning Indonesian will sit in the back row, still paying attention to the teacher's explanation, and not a few of them chat with friends near their seats. External factors that influence students' learning interest in Indonesian language lessons are from the family environment which receives less attention to learning because some parents migrate and entrust their children to relatives at home. The teacher's teaching method that prioritizes student activity has an effect on the learning process. Teachers also need the fulfillment of infrastructure and facilities to support the process of teaching and learning activities.

In the opinion of the class V teacher, that:
"As for facilities, learning Indonesian here is really inadequate because with what equipment this is, what's advanced in this digital era is because it's not yet complete, so there are still many deficiencies." (W.GKS)

SDN Banjaranyar 01 does not yet have an LCD and projector as a means of supporting learning making teachers feel difficult when playing internet and non-internet video footage which can reduce students' boredom in receiving Indonesian language material.

Based on documentation data, the results of learning Indonesian for class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency, most students get satisfactory grades because the scores they get are above the KKM. Students who get satisfactory learning outcomes have an interest in learning, because it is related to the students' skills in reading fluently. Students who are unable to read fluently or haltingly make student learning outcomes unsatisfactory which results in a lack of student interest in learning Indonesian.

There are two factors causing students' interest in learning Indonesian in

class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, namely internal (self) and external (outside oneself). Internal factors are caused by students who have not been able to read fluently, there are differences in intelligence and acceptance of the material, and the perceptions of students who are interested and less interested. Furthermore, external factors are influenced by the lack of attention to student learning, the teacher's teaching methods, and inadequate infrastructure.

Teacher Efforts to Increase Interest in Learning Indonesian Class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes Regency. There is an effort by the teacher to increase students' interest in learning Indonesian in class V at SDN Banjaranyar 01, one of which is by giving praise to students so that they can study well and achieve the desired future.

This is in accordance with the opinion of the class V teacher, that: "Yes, by giving praise to children. For example, answering correctly is good." (W.GK). Praise can motivate intrinsic interest in students making them excited to achieve a desired desire. Students will feel happy when they are praised because basically humans are happy if someone praises them, so that it can make students excited in the learning process activities. Nevertheless, the teacher still provides motivation for students' extrinsic interests such as awards, added value, or prizes.

The class V teacher stated that: " Yes, if the child can answer, I will give a prize, whether it is in the form of candy, chocolate, or money, in other words, to be enthusiastic in following the lesson. (W.GK). This method can make it easier for teachers to find out the conditions of student interest in learning which tend to be low, medium, or high. Students will pay attention to the teacher if the teacher can combine learning tools, methods and models that are adapted to the subject matter, according to the needs of students and teachers, and adjust students' abilities to accept Indonesian language subject matter.

Teachers can reduce students' boredom by telling stories about the meaning of life which leads to the formation of character education, looking for main topics discussing a problem, holding variations of learning, and holding nonverbal communication. Nevertheless, teachers still find students who are less interested in the lesson. How to deal with these problems according to the principal that: "With habituation, habituation. We try to make it a habit every morning to read together." (W.KS). Meanwhile, according to the fifth grade teacher said that: " To overcome this, we give story books so that children are more interested in learning ." (W.GK). The teacher uses a teaching and learning strategy by increasing the number of reading and writing activities supported by the school principal through the provision of a program of literacy activities every morning before learning activities begin (reading both fiction and non-fiction reading books). The school also organizes tutoring programs for lower grade students who cannot read fluently.

This is in accordance with the opinion of the class V teacher, that: " For low class there is. But for the high class, I think there's not enough time because the material is so dense, the targets must also be achieved, that's all ." (W.GK). Lower class students (grades I, II, and III) must be trained in terms of reading literacy. Because the relationship with the mental readiness of the student increases if he is good at reading and writing. Students' mental readiness is tested at the time of class promotion or even staying in class greatly affects the psychological condition of students. Moreover, the perception of parents who are embarrassed when their children leave the class because they cannot read fluently makes teachers feel confused about raising grades from low grade students to high grades.

According to the principal said that:

" Being trained has to do with the mental readiness of the child. It's possible that when grades I, II, III are still easy or when they're not ready, it's very difficult. But that actually should have been reminded from grade I but as soon as he went to class his mental readiness was already better. (W.KS)

Writing and reading activities are related to learning Indonesian not only in the aspect of communication skills but also in the interests of mastering science and knowledge related to the use of literacy as a basis for developing learning activities that assist students in their learning activities at school. Students who are fluent in reading and writing activities have the potential to be interested in learning Indonesian. Teachers can analyze the potential interest of students by measuring the level of interest in student learning. The way the teacher measures it can be done by looking at the characteristics of interest in learning that appear to be related to Indonesian language lessons during the learning process. The teacher as a teacher can identify the types of learning interests that are in accordance with the conditions of students so that they apply learning methods based on guidelines, resources, and teaching materials for teachers in make the RPP adjusted accordingly program Which planned according to the needs of students and teachers .

In the opinion of the fifth grade teacher:

" Here the methods used in learning Indonesian vary greatly. (W.GK). Through various sources, media, teaching aids, and teaching methods adapted to the needs of students and teachers, it is expected to be able to increase the interest in learning of fifth grade students, especially in the Indonesian language subject. Students who are interested in being able to improve the results of learning Indonesian.

Based on findings in the field, the class V teacher at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency made an effort to increase interest in learning Indonesian by carrying out reading literacy habits for 15 minutes before learning began and

the teacher directed students who had problems in reading comprehension to go to the library accompanied by the teacher BP.

Discussion

Based on the formulation of the problem in the introductory section, there are 3 sub-discussions related to the factors that cause interest in learning, the link between interest in learning and learning outcomes, and the teacher's efforts to increase interest in learning Indonesian.

Relation of Learning Interest with Indonesian Language Learning Outcomes Class V SD Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency. The results of the study show that there is an influence of interest on the results of learning Indonesian, because interest in learning is very important and influences students' desires related to the success of the learning process. Students who are interested will pay attention to the teacher's explanation and understand the material well which in the end will be able to obtain satisfying Indonesian learning results. Students who have a high learning interest produce better learning achievement and learning outcomes as evidenced by superior learning scores compared to students who are less interested in asking or answering teacher questions. If student interest decreases, then the learning outcomes become less than optimal .

This is consistent with Soebandi's theory (Dalam Sihombing dkk., 2021, hlm. 51) of learning interest influencing student learning outcomes because the higher the student's learning interest , the better also the learning outcomes . If the student 's interest decreases , then the learning outcomes become less than optimal . Interest in learning as the main factor that determines student activity. This is because the learning materials that are not in accordance with the interests of students are able to make students can not study well , because there is no attraction to learn it (Erlando Dalam Sihombing dkk., 2021, hlm. 51).

Students' interest in learning affects the results of learning Indonesian because the higher students have an interest in learning , the better the learning outcomes they have obtained. If students' interest decreases, their Indonesian language learning outcomes will also be less than optimal and their grades will also decrease. Interest in learning is important for teachers to know the high and low levels of interest related to the results of learning Indonesian obtained by students.

Student learning outcomes are the result of a process in which a number of factors influence each other. High or low one's learning outcomes are influenced by these factors. Russeefendi In (Susanto, 2019, hlm. 16) identifying the factors that influence learning outcomes into ten types, namely intelligence, child readiness, child talent, willingness to learn, child interest, model of material presentation, teacher personality and attitude, learning atmosphere, teacher competency, and community conditions. Of the ten factors, there are factors that have a major influence originating from the students themselves, including the child's intelligence, child readiness, and child talent. Factors that partially depend on the teacher, namely ability (competence), learning atmosphere, and teacher personality. The learning outcomes achieved are

influenced by the main factors in students in the form of their abilities and environmental factors have less influence on student learning outcomes.

In accordance with the research theory (Asrianti, 2020, hlm. 5) that learning Indonesian is inseparable from language skills that affect learning outcomes. Indonesian language learning has an important role not only in the aspect of communication skills but also in the interests of mastering knowledge and knowledge related to the use of literacy as a basis for developing learning activities that assist students in their learning activities at school. So that students who get high Indonesian learning outcomes have good mastery of communication skills and knowledge. Teachers should strive for high learning outcomes by increasing students' interest in learning Indonesian.

The results of learning Indonesian for class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 tend to be less than optimal because some students cannot read fluently. Some students are able to read fluently and the rest can read but still stammer. Indonesian language lessons have the characteristic of long reading considered by some students who feel that they are already fluent in reading they are able to master it. Most of the students scored above the KKM and got a higher grade predicate than in other subjects, because Indonesian is still a subject that some students like in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency.

Factors Causing Interest in Learning Indonesian Class V students at SDN Banjaranyar 01, Brebes Regency. The results of the study show that interest in learning is indispensable in the process of learning Indonesian because it can determine the learning conditions and factors that cause students' interest in learning Indonesian in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency. These factors come from within and outside yourself. Students' interest in learning is influenced by self-factors in the form of intentions in students accompanied by assumptions about Indonesian language subjects easy to learn, so they only rely on reading literacy skills that are already fluent. Some students also feel difficulty understanding Indonesian language subjects. Students who cannot read fluently are able to influence student learning interest, the characteristics of the Indonesian language contain long reading material, so it is difficult for students to get satisfactory learning results. Student learning interest is influenced by external factors in terms of teacher teaching methods that vary, are not monotonous, involve students in the learning process, a family environment that does not support student learning styles as a result of parents working overseas who entrust their children to family members at home, and lack of fulfillment of facilities and infrastructure at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency, such as the unfulfillment of LCDs and projectors at every grade level.

Matrona Dalam (Riyani dkk., 2021, hlm. 233) argued that there were two factors that influenced interest in learning, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors are factors that come from within the individual, whether physically, spiritually, physically or psychologically, while external factors are factors that come from outside the family, school and community. (Harefa dkk., 2020, hlm. 82) Student learning interest is influenced by internal factors, external factors. Internal factors such as students' initial ability to study material, good student emotional intelligence, student perceptions of a learning material,

parental attention, teacher presence, professional competence and teacher pedagogy in creating a learning process that is centered on student . F dominant external actor influencing interest learning is a slum environment and not child friendly can contribute significantly to the condition of students' interest in learning . According to (Marliana & Suhertuti, 2018)there are several factors that influence the management of learning related to interest in learning Indonesian, such as: curriculum, class/school buildings and facilities, teachers/teaching staff, students/students, class dynamics, and the surrounding environment.

The learning outcomes of fifth grade students at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency can be said to be unsatisfactory but not low. That is, students do not all have the level of intelligence and acceptance of the same material. Some students understand the teacher's explanation and the rest still need further explanation. Each student has differences regarding hobbies or interests in a particular lesson. Students who are interested in learning Indonesian material are able to follow the learning process well and have a high sense of enthusiasm as evidenced by the activeness of students in asking and answering teacher questions.

According to psychoanalytic theory , (A.M, 2020, hlm. 83) argues that human action as an interest in each individual has characteristics. Student interest in learning can be seen through the following characteristics : diligent in facing assignments , tenacious in facing difficulties , shows interest in various kinds of problems , prefers to work independently , quickly gets bored with routine tasks , can defend his opinion , does not easily let go of things he believes in , and likes to find and solve problems . According to Marx In (Akrim, 2021, hlm. 30)there are five characteristics of interest in learning, namely persistence in learning, tenacity in the face of difficulties, interest and sharpness in learning, achievement in learning, and independence in learning.

Interest contains three elements, namely elements of recognition, feelings, and will. Hidayat Dalam (Akrim, 2021, hlm. 31)divides these elements into several indicators related to one's interests, including: desire, feeling happy, attention, feeling interested, studying hard, doing assignments, and obeying rules. Priansa In (Baringbing dkk., 2022, hlm. 1067)the indicator of interest in learning consists of the desire to have something, participate in activities that are liked, know the types of activities in obtaining something, and make efforts to realize the desire or pleasure towards certain objects. There are several indicators of students according to (Islamiah, 2019, hlm. 453)those who have a high learning interest from the readiness of students to accept subject matter, student attendance while participating in learning, a sense of interest, ability, and enthusiasm of students to answer questions, student attention in the learning process, and student persistence in working on practice questions.

Some students who are less interested in learning Indonesian will sit in the back row, still paying attention to the teacher's explanation, and not a few of them chat with friends near their seats. External factors that influence students' learning interest in Indonesian language lessons are from the family environment which receives less attention to learning because some parents

migrate and entrust their children to relatives at home. The teacher's teaching method that prioritizes student activity has an effect on the learning process. Teachers also need the fulfillment of infrastructure and facilities to support the process of teaching and learning activities. SDN Banjaranyar 01 also does not yet have an LCD and projector as a means of supporting learning making teachers feel difficult when playing internet and non-internet video clips which can reduce students' boredom in receiving Indonesian language material.

The results of the analysis in this study are in accordance with the research theory of (Harefa dkk., 2020, hlm. 82) student learning interest influenced by internal factors such as students' initial ability to learn material, student perceptions, parental attention, teacher presence, and the external actor is the environment. Factors that influence interest in learning Indonesian according to (Marliana & Suhertuti, 2018), such as: curriculum, class or school buildings and facilities, teachers/teaching staff, students/students, class dynamics, and the surrounding environment.

There are two factors causing students' interest in learning Indonesian in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, namely internal (self) and external (outside oneself). Internal factors are caused by students who have not been able to read fluently, there are differences in intelligence and acceptance of the material, and the perceptions of students who are interested and less interested. External factors are influenced by the lack of attention to student learning, the teacher's teaching methods, and inadequate infrastructure.

Teachers' Efforts to Increase Students' Interest in Learning Indonesian in Class V at SDN Banjaranyar 01 Brebes Regency. The results showed that there were teacher efforts to increase students' interest in learning Indonesian in Indonesian language subjects in class V SDN Banjaranyar 01, one of which was by giving praise to students so they could study well and achieve the desired future. Praise can motivate intrinsic interest in students making them excited to achieve a desired desire. Students will feel happy when they are praised because basically humans are happy if someone praises them, so that it can make students excited in the learning process activities.

Guidance and development through Indonesian language subjects at all levels of education, especially in elementary schools, strives for 4 (four) types of language skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. This is stated in (Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Nasional Nomor 16 Tahun 2007 tentang Standar Kualifikasi Akademik dan Kompetensi guru) which includes the components of Indonesian language professional competence, covering aspects of listening, reading, speaking and writing.

Student learning interest in learning Indonesian is related to relatedness, pleasure, encouragement, in acquiring knowledge and skills that result in changes in attitudes and behavior in accordance with character education. Students are required to achieve competency in affective and psychomotor terms. It is hoped that the aim of learning Indonesian is not only to learn just knowledge or the surface, but to be imprinted in the real values of everyday life.

The teacher still provides motivation for students' extrinsic interests such

as awards, added value, or prizes. This method can make it easier for teachers to find out the conditions of student interest in learning which tend to be low, medium, or high. Students will pay attention to the teacher if the teacher can combine learning tools, methods and models that are adapted to the subject matter, according to the needs of students and teachers, and adjust students' abilities to accept Indonesian language subject matter.

In accordance with the opinion (Marliana & Suhertuti, 2018, hlm. 68) about the way the teacher arouses interest and keeps students' attention as follows: Using stories, analogies, something new, showing something different/odd that is different from the usual in learning.

Providing opportunities for students to participate actively in learning, for example students are invited to have discussions to choose topics to be discussed, ask questions or raise problems that need to be solved.

Carrying out variations in learning activities, for example according to Lesser as quoted by Gagne and Driscoll (1988:69) variations from serious to humorous, from fast to slow, from loud to moderate voices, and changing teaching styles.

Conduct nonverbal communication in learning activities such as demonstrations and simulations which according to Gagne and Briggs (1979: 157) can be done to attract students' interest/attention.

Teachers can reduce students' boredom by telling stories about the meaning of life which leads to the formation of character education, looking for main topics discussing a problem, holding variations of learning, and holding nonverbal communication. Teachers still find that students who are less interested in the lesson can be overcome by using teaching and learning strategies, such as increasing reading and writing activities through the provision of literacy training activities every morning for fifteen minutes before learning activities begin (reading both fiction and non-fiction reading books).

According to (Somadayo, 2020, hlm. 4) reading is an interactive activity to pick and understand the meaning or meaning contained in written material. Reading activity as a process that is carried out and used by the reader to get the message to be conveyed by the writer through the media of words or written material through visual activities, in the form of a series of eye movements in following the lines of writing, focusing on words and groups of words, reviewing words and groups of words to gain an understanding of the reading, as well as developing skills ranging from understanding words, sentences, paragraphs in the reading to understanding critically and evaluatively the entire contents of the reading.

A person is said to understand reading well if he has the ability to grasp the meaning of the words and expressions used by the author, understands explicit and implied meanings, and can draw conclusions. Nutal In (Somadayo, 2020, hlm. 11) stating that the purpose of reading is part of the process of reading comprehension, the reader obtains messages or meaning from it which can be in the form of information, knowledge, and even expressions of happy or sad messages. Reading should have a purpose because someone who reads

with a purpose tends to understand more than someone who doesn't have a goal.

In relation to the learning system in the classroom, teachers should be able to set specific goals that are appropriate or by helping them to set reading goals that include enjoyment, perfecting reading activities, using certain strategies, updating their knowledge of a topic, associating new information with information they already know, acquiring information for oral or written reports, confirming or rejecting predictions, presenting an experiment or applying information obtained from a text and answering specific questions.

Reading activities are related to learning Indonesian not only in the aspect of communication skills but also in the interests of mastering science and knowledge related to the use of literacy as a basis for developing learning activities that assist students in their learning activities at school. Students who are fluent in reading and writing activities have the potential to be interested in learning Indonesian. Teachers can analyze the potential interest of students by measuring the level of interest in student learning. The way the teacher measures it can be done by looking at the characteristics of interest in learning that appear to be related to Indonesian language lessons during the learning process.

Interested students according to psychoanalytic theory, (A.M, 2020, hlm. 83) characterized by: diligent in facing the task, tenacious in the face of difficulties, shows interest in various kinds of problems, prefers to work independently, quickly gets bored with routine tasks, can defend his opinion, does not easily let go of things he believes in, and likes to find and solve problems. In addition, teachers can also measure students' interest in learning by identifying types of interest in learning to increase student interest in learning, especially in Indonesian language lessons.

According to (Akrim, 2021, hlm. 21) that there are three types of interest in learning, including:

Visual learning interest, namely learning interest that relies on observation by using the sense of sight to be able to understand and remember it. This interest in learning must first be shown concrete evidence and make lots of symbols and pictures in the notes.

Interest in auditory learning, namely learning interest that relies on the sense of hearing to be able to understand and remember something. These learning interests usually prefer to record with tapes rather than taking notes, because they like to listen to information that is repeated).

Kinesthetic learning interest, namely learning interest that utilizes the limbs of the human body to understand something. This interest in learning does not like sitting still for long because they have a desire to be active and explore.

The teacher as a teacher can identify the types of learning interests that are in accordance with the conditions of students so that they apply learning methods based on guidelines, resources, and teaching materials for teachers in

make the RPP adjusted accordingly program Which planned according to the needs of students and teachers . Through various sources, media, teaching aids, and teaching methods adapted to the needs of students and teachers, it is expected to be able to increase the interest in learning of fifth grade students, especially in the Indonesian language subject .

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

There is a relationship between interest and learning outcomes obtained by fifth grade students, right now already satisfactory as evidenced by the acquisition of scores above the KKM in the student master book. High learning outcomes are influenced by students' interest in learning Indonesian. There are factors that cause interest in learning, namely internal factors from within students' self-intention to learn Indonesian. While external factors from the outside are influenced by various teacher teaching methods, family environmental conditions that pay little attention to student learning styles, and the lack of completeness of infrastructure in schools. The teacher's efforts to increase interest in learning Indonesian by holding literacy culture habituation before learning activities begin for fifteen minutes and the teacher directs students who have problems in reading comprehension to go to the library accompanied by the BP teacher.

Reccomendations

There are several suggestions for related parties, including for teachers , using various group methods , creating creative and innovative learning media, and seeking in-depth understanding along with students who have differences in understanding the directions and explanations from the teacher. For schools, do fulfillment facilities and infrastructure such as LCD and projectors at each grade level. For advanced researchers , they can examine further about student learning interests related to improving Indonesian language learning outcomes obtained to be optimal and satisfying, and learning outcomes can be investigated further in depth about students' learning interests based on indicators of learning outcomes , such as talent or will.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The completion of the research that has been carried out cannot be separated from the prayers and support from various parties. Therefore, the researcher expresses his gratitude to Allah SWT and thanks the private researcher who has struggled to finish up to this stage. Thank you also to the parents of the researchers, supervisors, schools who have assisted in research activities, and all parties who have helped in the process of completing this research.

REFERENCES

- Agustin, R., Nurmalina, & Noviardila, I. (2021). The Role of Animation Interactive Media on Learning Interest in Indonesian Language Subjects in Class IV Students of SD Negeri 019 Tanjung Sawit, Tapung District, Kampar Regency Learning 2020/2021. *JPdK: Journal of Education and Counseling* , 3 (1), 71-79. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31004/jpdk.v3i1.1385>
- Akrim. (2021). Strategies for Increasing Students' Learning Interests Learning PAI Create Student Character (E. Sulasmi, Ed.; 1st ed.). CV. Group Science Library.
- AM, S. (2020). Teaching and Learning Interaction & Motivation (1 ed.). PT. King of Grafindo Persada.
- Asrianti. (2020). Learners' Learning Interest in Literacy-Based Indonesian Language Learning. *ETHNOLINGUAL JOURNAL* , 4 (1), 1-14.
- Astina, RZ, Sungkowo, & Andriyadi. (2021). Increasing Students' Interest in Learning Indonesian Subjects Through Newspaper Media in Class III at Public Elementary School 119/VIII Tirta Kencana Rimbo Bujang. *el-Madib:Journal of Islamic Elementary Education* , 1 (2), 30-51. <https://ejurnal.iaiyasnibungo.ac.id/index.php/el-Madib/article/view/349/236>
- Baringbing, A., Abi, AR, & Silaban, PJ (2022). Factor Analysis of Students' Low Learning Interest in Mathematics Class VI Elementary School. *JURNAL PAJAR (Education and Teaching)* , 6 (4), 1065-1072. <https://doi.org/10.33578/pjr.v6i4.8577>
- Harefa, N., Tafonao, SG, & Hidar, S. (2020). Analysis of Students' Interest in Learning Chemistry Through Multimedia-Based Learning. *Paedagogia: Journal of Educational Studies, Research and Development* , 11 (2), 81-86. <https://doi.org/10.31764>

- Harjanto, D., Istiatin, & Sarsono. (2021). Motivation, Independence, Interest in Learning and Learning Methods to the Learning Achievements of Students of SMA Batik 2 Surakarta. *Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR) Peer Reviewed-International Journal* , 5 (3), 1-9. <https://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/IJEBAR>
- Islamia, ID (2019). The Effect of Student Learning Interest on Mathematics Learning Achievement at SMKN 1 Cihampelas. *Journal On Education* , 1 (2), 451-457. <https://jonedu.org/index.php/joe/article/view/91>
- Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System . (yyyy).
- Marliana, L., & Suhertuti. (2018). *Indonesian Language Teaching and Learning Strategies* (1 ed.). PT. Rosdakarya youth.
- Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 16 of 2007 concerning Academic Qualification Standards and Teacher Competency . (yyyy).
- Risnanosanti, Abdullah, AR, Yumnah, S., Hariko, R., Salam, MF, Togatorop, F., Hutagalung, ISR, Darojah, RU, Murtandha, R., Mustova, Zulaichoh, Haeran, & Halim, FA (2022). *Development of Student Learning Interests and Talents* (1 ed.). CV. Eternal Archipelago Literacy.
- Riyani, R., Sultan, MA, & Yulia, H. (2021). Analysis of Student Learning Interest in Online Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic at the Elementary School Level. *PINISI JOURNAL OF EDUCATION238LIST* , 1 (1), 231-238.
- Sihombing, S., Silalahi, HR, Sitinjak, JR, Tambunan, H., & Hutauruk, A. (2021). Analysis of Interest and Learning Motivation, Understanding of Concepts and Student Creativity on Student Learning Outcomes in Geometry Material During Class X SMA Medan Network Learning. *SEPREN: Journal of Mathematics Education and Applied* , 02 (02), 50-66. <https://jurnal.uhn.ac.id/index.php/sepren/article/view/555/263>
- Slameto. (2020). *Learning and Influencing Factors* . PT. Rineka Cipta.
- Somadayo, S. (2020). *Reading Learning Strategies and Techniques* .
- Susanto, A. (2019). *Theory of Learning and Learning in Elementary Schools* (3rd ed.). Prenadamedia Group.
- Sutina, BYR, Makki, M., & Safruddin, S. (2022). Analysis of Learners' Learning Interest in Class IV Indonesian Subject at SDN 1 Wanasaba Daya for the 2022/2023 Academic Year. *Scientific Journal of the Educational Profession* , 7 (3c), 1973-1978. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jipp.v7i3c.854>

Warsadi. (2019). Indonesian Language Learning Achievement: The Effect of Learning Interest and Learning Motivation. *Discourse: Journal of Indonesian Language Education* , 2 (3), 267-275.